

ENABLING UNIVERSAL HEALTH CARE FROM A PROVINCE-WIDE HEALTH SYSTEM PERSPECTIVE

by Mary Camille Samson, Rosario Dizon, and Dr. Helena Marie Lagon Alviator

Since the passage of the Universal Health Care (UHC) Law in 2019, there have been numerous initiatives to demonstrate the integration of the fragmented local health systems in the Philippines. Guidelines and policies aiming to highlight the importance of primary health care in a mature health system have also been released. Four years into the implementation of the UHC Law, UHC Integration Sites in the country have been making strides in functionalizing their respective provincial health boards to oversee the province-wide health systems, strengthen health service delivery within the health care provider network, and strategically invest for the health needs of the population. However, realizing the intended reforms of the Law is still an uphill climb.

As local consultants for the Western Visayas region, we aim to contribute by scoping out UHC gains and key technical assistance result areas feasible within a short-term engagement. We identified the regional offices of the Department of Health (DOH) and PhilHealth as our main stakeholders in this endeavor. We also built on the partnership made with the Province of Guimaras to get a more grounded perspective of assistance needed at the local level. Discussions with our identified stakeholders in the region circled around these three questions which also facilitated the scope of work we intend to do in the next three to six months.

1 How do we approach province-wide integration?

As local governments navigate their way through the UHC road, the national government is equally challenged to revisit existing paradigms and shift towards a province-wide network of care lens. The national government has been mandated to develop standards for the health system and expand benefit packages to cover a wider range of services. The status quo of doing things is tackling it one program or indicator at a time. Moving to a more integrated approach, all health stakeholders are compelled to transition from handling health interventions and reforms in a vertical-programmatic approach to a more holistic and system perspective. Health officers and health board members are asked to sift through guidelines and policies from the national government and ultimately implement and operationalize these policies.

What is the service capacity of facilities in each province?

2 Primary health care is put at the forefront of this UHC reform and established as the foundation of our local health system. However, there remains to be a missing piece in the picture of the true capacity at the primary care level. The DOH has licensing requirements for primary care facilities (PCF) while PhilHealth has been purchasing primary care services through its Konsulta package. The network of facilities in the province and its health officers will benefit from knowing the service capacities of each PCF to facilitate appropriate referrals and improve the navigation of patients seeking medical care. With the limited resources for health, streamlining the requirements and processes for licensing and accreditation of health facilities and providers will help the local government and the health board to be more strategic in investing on health system inputs for the province.

Who will support the local governments to improve the access to and quality of health facilities in an integrated network of care?

3 The range of roles and responsibilities of Development Management Officers (DMOs) range from policy advocacy, network and collaboration, and technical assistance to local governments and monitoring of local health systems. Specific to UHC implementation, the DMOs are members of local health boards and are key persons in integrating local health systems at the provincial level. Aside from cascading national policies and guidelines to local governments, DMOs also have an important role to advocate for them and feedback their innovations and challenges to the DOH for consideration in succeeding policy issuances. The roles of DMOs cannot be discounted, hence, these key movers need to be supported in terms of identifying their personal learning, development, and training needs so that they can effectively perform their expected roles in the context of local health system integration and UHC implementation.

In continuing the engagement, we can further contribute to the areas of facility capacity assessment and to the capacity development of local technical assistance providers. We look to run a practical assessment of the PCF service capacities in an island province in Western Visayas. This exercise aims to give a province-wide perspective in terms of licensing/certification/accreditation status and solicit recommendations from stakeholders to upgrade service delivery in each PCF in the province. Parallel to this, we also target to strengthen the capacity of the DMOs as technical assistance providers to their respective areas of assignment. This will be achieved through a collaborative endeavor with the DOH regional office.

Key Activity Highlights

Engagement Period: November–December 2023

Courtesy and Exploratory Meetings with Region VI Stakeholders

- In November 2023, we visited key regional health agency stakeholders, DOH-Center for Health Development Western Visayas (DOH-CHD 6) and the PhilHealth Regional Office (PRO 6), with discussions focused on UHC implementation strategies, regional capacity-building needs, and potential areas for collaboration.
- The DOH-CHD 6 specifically sought our participation in upcoming regional meetings, and support to the HSIMEC in the capacity-building for its staff and the DMOs to advance UHC implementation in respective provinces.
- There is continued interest in the implementation learnings from the Guimaras Konsulta Primary Care Provider Network (PCPN) Sandbox. The PRO 6 verbalized technical assistance areas aligned with this and its potential application to the upcoming Health Care Provider Network (HCPN) Demo Site Sandbox in Aklan. Though seemingly separate approaches, it would be beneficial for region-wide health leaders to foster a community of practice around these sandboxes to strengthen UHC gains across Western Visayas.

[from top to bottom] Courtesy and Exploratory Meetings with stakeholders from DOH-CHD 6, PRO 6, Guimaras Provincial Health Office, and Western Visayas PBSP Team

Key Activity Highlights

Engagement Period: November–December 2023

Support to Provincial UHC Summits: Capiz and Guimaras

- December 2023 marked a month of significant strides in the Philippines' UHC journey. As the global community celebrated Universal Health Coverage Day on December 12th, we actively participated in the provincial UHC Summits of Capiz (December 13th) and Guimaras (December 15th), solidifying our commitment to local-level UHC implementation. These summits provided crucial platforms for identifying challenges and solutions to address specific needs in each province.

Recognition given to the team for UHC implementation support in Guimaras under the ThinkWell project. [L-R] Dr. Sheila Gumabong (PHO I), Dr. Adriano Suba-an (DOH CHD-6 Regional Director), Gov. JC Rahman Nava, and Dr. Lester Tan (DOH Central Office BLHSD)

Local PBSP Team [L-R] Dr. Helena Marie Alvior (Technical Advisor), Ms. Mary Camille Samson (Program Analyst), and Ms. Rosario Dizon (Project Coordinator)

Dr. Alvior moderating the panel discussion during the Capiz UHC Summit

Guimaras panelists together with Dr. Helena Marie Alvior who moderated the session of the UHC Summit

- Capiz UHC Summit Unveils Challenges:** The Capiz UHC summit identified roadblocks to smooth implementation. Outdated referral processes and leadership gaps surfaced as critical concerns, causing delays and ineffectiveness. Capiz seeks to address these issues by conducting several consultative meetings and hiring a technical writer to update their HCPN manual and referral mechanisms.
- Exploring Innovative UHC Financing in Guimaras:** The Guimaras summit delved into approaches to UHC financial integration. The provincial accountant's insights highlighted transparency and accountability as critical in the management design of the province-wide health system's Special Health Fund (SHF). Local Chief Executives reiterated their support and willingness to integrate local resources. Health stakeholders present were apprised of the Konsulta PCPN Sandbox main implementation hurdle, citing the escrow or surety bond requirement a challenge for a 4th class province.
- The provincial UHC summits yielded invaluable insights into the region's UHC journey. Recognizing that each province faces unique challenges, UHC implementation strategies must be tailored to local needs and supported by strong leadership and governance. Continuous knowledge generation and collaboration, fueled by sharing of good practices, are key to accelerating progress.

Key Activity Highlights

Engagement Period: November–December 2023

Participation in the Regional Implementation and Coordination Team (RICT) Meeting

Attendees of the Regional Implementation and Coordination Team Meeting last December 17, 2023 at J7 Plaza Hotel, Mandurriao, Iloilo City.

- Stakeholders from different government agencies and health partners in the region attended the RICT meeting organized by the DOH CHD 6. With the invitation to participate, we welcomed the opportunity to be updated on national and regional directions, and to foster inter-agency collaboration for health.
- **The Health Sector 8-Point Agenda:** DOH's medium-term strategy for 2023–2028 puts every Filipino at the core of the healthcare reforms, which will be enabled through community involvement and strong commitment of health workers. This action agenda is aligned with the ongoing Universal Health Care reform being pursued by UHC Integration Sites (IS) in the country. In Western Visayas region, all six provinces are UHC IS.
- **Status of Primary Care Provider Network in Western Visayas:** A PhilHealth representative was assigned to give an update on this, and the Local Health Insurance Officer presented the progress of Guimaras province in terms of preparing the health network for PhilHealth contracting while continuing the implementation of the 'regular' Konsulta program. Health providers present in the meeting, and particularly the Association of Municipal Health Officers of the Philippines (AMHOP) president, resonated with the challenges encountered by Guimaras health facilities such as difficulties in encoding patient health information for record-keeping and in receiving the capitation payment.
- **Transfer of DOH Financial Grants to the SHF:** Through Department Memorandum 2023-0403, the DOH has authorized the CHDs to transfer DOH financial grants to the SHF of integrated Province/City-wide Health Systems (P/CWHS) starting fiscal year 2024. Among the grants that may be transferred to the SHF are the 2024 Fixed Tranche, UHC IS Financial Grants, and other DOH financial support to LGUs. This initiative from the DOH presents an opportunity for health boards and their respective Management Support Units to practice stewardship of their P/CWHS and realize financial integration in the implementation of UHC.

In harnessing shared learnings and collaboration, the Western Visayas region can collectively make transformative leaps towards achieving the progressive realization of UHC for every Filipino. We remain committed to this journey of recommending tailored solutions and providing expertise to empower local health partners.